

PREDICTION OF COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT STRENGTH BASED ON INSTABILITY OF DELAMINATION

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1 Introduction

CFRP laminates are used in aerospace industry due to their high specific strength and stiffness. The laminates are susceptible to a foreign object impact. Barely visible impact damage (BVID) is one of the most severe damages for damage tolerance design of aircraft structures. The damage causes a significant reduction of compressive strength of laminates. However, the detail of the failure mechanism during compression-after-impact (CAI) test is not well known. For aircraft structures, demands of damage tolerance performance are too hard, so weight savings of airframe are not realized sufficiently in the case CAI strength is used for structure design.

Compressive strength reduction of impact damaged laminates has been studied by many researchers experimentally and analytically [1]-[11]. Impact damage consists of many delaminations and matrix cracks, and it forms like double spiral stair case [8][9]. Ishikawa et al. showed characteristic buckling mode of impacted laminate by observing the deformation and using finite element method [9]. Suemasu et al. studied postbuckling behavior of laminate with multiple delaminations using Reyleigh-Ritz method and finite element analysis [10][11]. They showed relationships between number of delamination or diameter of delamination and buckling load of laminate respect to symmetric and anti-symmetric buckling mode. Recently, more complicate damage model has been simulated with development of computing machine [12]-[17]. Suemasu et al. [14][15] analyzed postbuckling behavior of laminate with multiple circular delaminations considering propagation of delamination using interface elements. Craven et al. [16] studied buckling mode and buckling load of laminate with realistic delamination and fiber fracture crack. They modeled

the damage as multiple peanut shaped delaminations and star shaped cracks. Ichiki et al. numerically studied postbuckling behavior and residual strength of CFRP laminates with a simplified impact damage, that is, double-spiral-damage [17][18]. CAI strength reduction and failure mechanism were discussed using energy release rate of delamination edges and stress concentration near the damage.

The aim of this study is to investigate what happen before final failure of CFRP laminates with impact damage to predict CAI strength by numerical simulation. The compression performance of CFRP laminates with double-spiral damage is studied considering the instability of the damage. First, the postbuckling behavior of impact damaged laminates and the energy release rate distribution along delamination edge and the instability of delamination are reviewed first. Then, the failure processes simulated by using interface element are shown and failure process and the mechanism will be discussed.

2 Finite element analysis

Quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates of 32 plies $[45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{4S}$ with a double-spiral-damage were analyzed using finite element method. Dimensions and boundary conditions of the numerical model were determined based on the SACMA standard of CAI test specimen (SRM 2R-94), and these are shown in Fig. 1. Ply thickness was 0.15mm. Material properties of plies are $E_L=137\text{GPa}$, $E_T=8.21\text{GPa}$, $G_{LT}=4.36\text{GPa}$, $G_{TT}=2.41\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{LT}=0.33$, and $\nu_{TT}=0.41$ [18].

The impact damage was modeled as a double-spiral-damage (DSD). DSD consists of octant delaminations and matrix cracks as shown in Fig. 2. Circular undamaged portion was left at the center as mentioned by [8][9]. Its diameter was set $d_i=5.0$ mm.

Fig. 1 Finite element discretization

Fig. 2 Double-spiral-damage $d=30\text{mm}$ (DSD30)

Outer diameters of delaminations were modeled so as to increase gradually from the front side to the backside. Two sizes of the damage were calculated. The average diameters d were 30 mm (DSD30: $d_o = 25.5\sim 34.5$ mm) and 40mm (DSD40: $d_o = 35.5\sim 44.5$ mm), respectively.

The finite element analysis was performed by ABAQUS/Standard. Laminate was used 20-node brick elements. Uniform compressive displacement was applied to the loading edge. Small distributed load was applied to the top surface at the center of the plate to give a small out-of-displacement. Geometrical nonlinearity and contact condition of delaminated surfaces were considered in the analysis.

Zero-thickness interface elements with 16 nodes to calculate delamination growth were used in the damage growth simulation. The element had 121 (11×11) integration points to accurately approximate internal stress. Bilinear relation of traction-

separation was used. Onset and propagation criteria of delamination under mixed mode condition were expressed by quadratic form of traction and power law form of energy release rate component, respectively. Critical energy release rate of opening and shear components were set $G_{IC}=0.4\text{kJ/m}^2$ and $G_{IIC}=1.8\text{kJ/m}^2$, respectively, which are interlaminar fracture toughness of IM600/133 [19].

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Postbuckling behavior

The deflections of the model DSD30 are plotted against applied load in Fig. 3. A deformed shape of the damaged portion of the buckled plate is shown in Fig. 4. Out-of-plane displacements of 5 points (Center, A, B, Front side, and Back side) are indicated in Fig. 4. Broken line is the center deflection of intact plate. Dot lines without marks show post-buckling paths of the five points when damage did not grow. The lines with marks are out-of-displacement of the five points when the damage growth was considered.

Surface buckling occurred at very low compressive load because the delaminated layers near the surfaces were very thin compared to the other inside delaminated layers. When applied load was about 100 kN, displacement of the center of the plate started increasing gradually, while the displacements outside the damage were very small. So, we named this stage “local through-thickness buckling”.

The laminate deformed globally after applied load exceeded 220 kN when damage growth was not considered. The displacement of the center of the plate started decreasing at about 250 kN. The two points A and B displaced in the opposite directions. Finally, the laminate deformed took an anti-symmetrical shape. If damage did not grow, the post-buckling behavior of impact damaged laminates would consist of four stages;

- (a) The surface buckling
- (b) The through-thickness local buckling
- (c) The symmetrical global buckling
- (d) The anti-symmetrical global buckling.

If the laminate is sufficiently thick, the damage growth probably occurs before the global buckling.

3.2 Energy release rate distribution

Fig. 3 Relationships between applied load and deflections of DSD30

Fig. 4 Local buckling of damaged portion (120 kN)

Fig. 5 shows energy release rate distributions along inside and outside edges of the delaminations when the applied load was 140kN. Horizontal axis is the angle from the transverse crack of central layer. Vertical axis is the energy release rate. The angles written above the graph show the fiber direction of

the corresponding ply. The energy release rate at the inside edges (*G-in*) was much higher than the outside edge. So, the inside edges of the damage tend to grow and the counter delaminations merge at early stage of the local through-thickness buckling. The energy release rate tended to be large near the mid-plane, while delaminations near the surfaces had high energy release rate due to local surface buckling. The energy release rate at the outside edge (*G-out*) was high at the transverse edges ($\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$), while at the inside edges was high in the longitudinal edges ($0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$). The delaminations locating inside the laminate closed and only surface delaminations opened. Therefore, the energy release rate of the delaminations near the surfaces had mode I component, and others were dominated by shear component.

Fig. 6 shows peak values of the energy release rate of the outside transverse edges. The positions were numbered from the top to the bottom as illustrated in Fig. 5. Portion 1 locates next to the impact side and portion 7 is nearest to the backside. After the surface buckling, the energy release rate at portion 1 and 7 started increasing gradually. The energy release rate was high at portion 7 which had largest delamination. The energy release rate of all portions increased rapidly after the local buckling occurred at 230 MPa for DSD30 and at 140 MPa for DSD40. The increasing rate tended to be higher for the smaller delaminations. The energy release rate of DSD40 was much larger than that of DSD30 when load was same. Unstable damage growth was expected, because the energy release rate increased with the delamination growth. CAI strengths

Fig. 5 Energy release distribution at 140 kN

Fig. 6 Increase of energy release rate of delamination edges and relationships between CAI strength and interlaminar fracture toughness

Fig. 7 Prediction of failure strength and experimental result

obtained by the test were plotted against the mode II critical energy release rate G_{IIc} for several laminates in Fig. 6 [18]. These relationships were well correlated with the present results obtained by finite element analysis.

The compressive stress in the 0° layers at the both side of damage was checked and found to become large. We obtained the applied stress when the maximum compressive stress reached the compressive strength of the quasi-isotropic laminates of IM600/133. Fig. 7 shows a rough estimate of failure strength when the laminate breaks due to the concentrated compressive stress.

Horizontal broken lines show the expected compressive failure stress for DSD30 and DSD40. Compressive failure can occur or interact with the delamination instability if interlaminar fracture toughness is very high.

3.3 Damage propagation

Damage propagation process obtained from the damage growth analysis is shown in Fig. 8. The completely failed interface elements colored and the color bar shows the location of delaminations. The delaminations near the bottom surface started growing at about 100~120 kN due to the surface buckling. The delamination at the second interface from the top surface a little propagated inward and the damages at the third interfaces from the both surfaces grew outward. After the through-thickness local buckling, the damage propagated gradually. The inside delamination edges propagated in the loading direction. In particular, the delaminations near the mid-plane grew faster. Some pairs of delaminations merged at about 150 kN as shown in Fig. 9(b). The transverse edge of damage propagated outward as shown in Fig. 9 (a). At the beginning of damage propagation, the delaminations at the third interface from the both surfaces propagated due to the opening of the delamination tip. All the delaminations of the transverse grew after the through-thickness local buckling. Moreover, it seemed that the growth of delaminations near the impact side was larger than near the backside. These results were well correlated with the results of energy release rate distribution. The calculation could not be converged after the whole damage rapidly propagated to the transverse direction at 157kN. Consequently the analysis terminated. It is thought that the damage grows stably before unstable propagation of the damage occurs.

In fact, the stable growth of the impact damage before final failure of laminate was observed in CAI test. Fig. 10 shows an ultrasonic image of the damage propagation [20]. In this experiment, it was observed that the shape of the Initial damage did not change significantly until applied load was about 100 kN. After the delamination grew a little, the unstable propagation of the whole damage to the full width occurred instantly. This was probably the trigger of the final failure of impact damaged laminate.

Fig. 8 Damage propagation of DSD30

(a) Interface 7 (-45°/90°) (b) Interface 14 (0°/-45°)

Fig. 9 Delamination propagation at 157 kN

3.4 Prediction of CAI strength by simulation of damage growth using explicit method.

To investigate failure process including unstable damage growth, a simulation by ABAQUS/Explicit was carried. In this analysis, 8-node continuum shell elements were used for the laminate. 8-node

(a) Specimen 1 (Top view)

(b) Specimen 2 (Bottom view)

Fig. 10 Ultrasonic image of the damage propagation during CAI test (IM600/133, 6.7J/mm) [20]

cohesive elements were set to the interfaces of the laminate and in the layer where the matrix cracks were expected to occur. Mass scaling was used. Fig. 11 shows relationships between applied load and end-shortening. Broken line and dark solid line show the load-displacement relationship of an intact plate and the damaged laminate without damage growth, respectively. “Implicit” and “Explicit” show the relationships between the load and end-shortening for the damaged laminates with considering damage growth obtained by an implicit and explicit method. Critical load obtained by the explicit method was slightly smaller than that by the implicit method. The explicit method could show the unloading path due to the unstable damage growth. The reason why the implicit analysis stopped due to the difficulty of the convergence is thought to be the unstable damage growth at the point.

Relationships between compressive stress and strain obtained from CAI test of IM600/133 specimen [20] are compared with the present result obtained by the explicit method in Fig. 12. The strains were measured on the both surfaces at a point beside the damage and 20 mm from the center of the plate. The present results well correlated with the experiment.

Fig. 13 shows the propagation history of the delamination 7 obtained by the explicit method. At the load of 132 kN, a small damage growth was observed as obtained by the implicit method. The delaminations grew stably up until all the delaminations simultaneously and unstably started growing to the transverse direction at 140 kN. The load decreased with the damage growth. The history of the whole damage with the load increase is shown in Fig. 14. When the load was below 130 kN, no damage shape grew. Then, the damage grew inward and center portion was fully delaminated at 137 kN. The load was much lower than the load obtained from the implicit method. It is because propagation of the matrix cracks was considered in the explicit analysis while growth of matrix crack was not considered in the implicit analysis. The size of the damage at the unstable propagation onset was almost same as that the analysis stopped due to the difficulty of convergence. Unstable damage growth occurs after a small damage growth. The analytical results without damage growth may give some error but the difference of the failure load is not significant.

4 Conclusions

The postbuckling behavior and the failure process of CFRP laminate with the double-spiral shape damage were numerically simulated considering damage growth. It is revealed that the damage grows stably by some extent before the final failure of the laminate occurred. However, the growth was not significant and we can estimate the failure load with a sufficient accuracy from the analytical results without damage growth.

Fig. 11 Relationships between applied load and displacement of loading edge (DSD30)

Fig. 12 Comparison of stress-strain curve obtained from CAI test and FEM

Considering the numerical cost, the results are worth. The matrix crack propagation is necessary to be considered to get accurate solution. Also compressive damage in 0° layer may be necessary to be considered, because maximum compressive strain can be sufficiently large that the reduction of compressive elasticity is necessary to be considered.

Fig. 13 Unstable propagation of delamination at interface 7 (-45°/90°)

Fig. 14 Overall view of the whole damage growth

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